

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL OBSERVATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Pedagogical observation is a peculiar method of pedagogy. Therefore, here it is necessary to pay attention to the term method itself. Method (from the Greek *methodos* - path) is the path of knowledge, the method of constructing and substantiating scientific knowledge, the method by which the subject of science is known¹. Research methods are those ways, methods and means by which new knowledge is obtained, facts that are used to prove the provisions that, in turn, form a scientific theory. The effectiveness of science largely depends on the development of research methods, on how quickly and effectively it is able to perceive and use all the latest that appears in the methods of other sciences. Where this can be done, there is also a breakthrough towards the comprehension of new knowledge.

Pedagogical supervision. This is one of the most common and most accessible methods for researching teaching practice in teaching English. During observation, the main attention should be paid to:

- How do students behave during class?
- How students pronounce difficult and complex words?
- What are the students interested in?
- Which pictures primarily have a positive effect on the student?
- The psychological state of each student, etc.

Pedagogical observation during the teaching of English is a direct perception, knowledge of the pedagogical process in natural conditions (for example, in the learning process, extracurricular activities, etc.). Observation requires the researcher to accurately fix the facts, objective pedagogical analysis. However, this is not an easy task. Observation in pedagogical research can be aimed at achieving various goals. It can be used as a source of information for building hypotheses, serve to test the data obtained by other methods, it can be used to extract additional information about the object under study.

In the process of teaching a foreign language - observation is a rather laborious research method. The difficulties of using observation as a method of collecting primary information are a consequence of its features and are divided into:

¹ Rubenstein SL. Fundamentals of General Psychology: In 2 volumes - m., 1989. - V.1. - Wp. 44.

subjective, associated with the personality of the researcher and objective, independent of the researcher.

The subjective difficulties of observation include the fact that the researcher understands and interprets the behavior and actions of, say, pupils through the prism of his own "I", through his system of value orientations. First of all, the limited time of observation should be attributed to the objective difficulties of observation. In addition, not all pedagogical facts lend themselves to direct observation. In order to obtain the information necessary for the purposes of the study, not to miss any important facts or significant information of the object under study, it is necessary to develop a program of pedagogical observation in advance.

Drawing up an observation program puts the researcher in front of the need to: - solve a number of fairly complex problems; - to study the object of study comprehensively, in various conditions and situations; - to build a classification system of facts, phenomena that meet the objectives of the study. - test the viability of the hypothesis; - establish the timing of the observation and determine the means of collecting information. There are many types of observation. According to the degree of coverage, observation can be: continuous (when the researcher's attention is drawn, say, to the entire class (group) and selective (when an individual student and a small group of children are being monitored).

According to the regularity of the conduct, one can distinguish between systematic and random observation. Systematic observation is characterized primarily by the regularity of fixing actions, situations, processes over a certain period of time. It allows you to identify the dynamics of processes, significantly increase the reliability of extrapolation of their development. Random observation refers to the observation of a previously unplanned phenomenon, activity, pedagogical situation. In other words, random observation is usually not planned as an independent procedure for collecting primary information. According to the degree of formalization, observation can be unstructured (uncontrolled), in which the researcher does not determine in advance which elements of the process (situation) under study he will observe. It does not have a strict plan. Structured (controlled) is a type of observation in which the researcher determines in advance which of the elements of the process or situation being studied are of the greatest importance for his research, and focuses his attention on them, drawing up a special plan for recording observations before collecting information.

Observation is either direct or indirect. Direct observation is characterized by the fact that the researcher studies the process directly. Indirect observation is characterized by the fact that the teacher learns about the features of the phenomenon under study through other persons. The advantage of direct observation is that it allows you to study the activities and behavior of people directly, i.e. to study those of their features, which, for example, in conversations or questionnaires, they do not mention them.

During the teaching of English, for five minutes in the middle of the lesson, covert observation is advisable. Covert surveillance - this surveillance is carried out unnoticed by students. It is this observation that is of value. Here the researcher adheres to the rule: strive to see, being invisible. It simply registers the course of events.

The covert surveillance process should include the following step-by-step procedure:

First stage. The teacher at the beginning of the school year purposefully and systematically collects material. Information is recorded and accumulated in the diaries of pedagogical observations.

Second phase. The teacher systematizes, classifies the information received, analyzes the factors that contribute to the development of negative qualities of the student's personality, external features of behavior, establishes a connection between them in order to penetrate into the essence of the phenomenon. For example, he reflects on the causes of difficult education, builds conclusions.

Third stage. The teacher, on the basis of receiving information and its analysis, predicts educational work with students, analyzes their shortcomings and advantages².

Thus, observation makes it possible to trace the development of the personality of a student or student group. Without observation, it is difficult to evaluate students.

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² Goodwin J. Research in psychology: methods and planning. St. Petersburg: Peter, 2004.

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